

FEATURES OF PHYSIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN STUDENTS DURING ADOLESCENCE

Rakhmonova Ayshakhan Oribovna

Head of the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences,
Kokan State Pedagogical Institute.

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Abstract. The article reveals the features of physiological and psychological changes in students during adolescence. Teenagers have some physical, mental and political advantages over their predecessors. It is shown that they have earlier sexual maturation, the process of socialization and mental development. Adolescence is a period of sexual maturation, characterized by the emergence of new feelings, intuitions and complex issues related to sexuality.

Key words: adolescence, student, physiological, psychological, character, physical, intellectual, political, sexual, adulthood, feelings, intuition, sexual life.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ В ПОДРОСТКОВОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

Аннотация. В статье раскрываются особенности физиологических и психологических изменений у студентов в подростковом возрасте. Подростки имеют некоторые физические, умственные и политические преимущества перед своими предшественниками. Показано, что у них происходит более раннее половое созревание, процесс социализации и психического развития. Подростковый возраст — период полового созревания, характеризующийся появлением новых чувств, интуиции и сложных вопросов, связанных с сексуальностью.

Ключевые слова: подростковый возраст, студент, физиологический, психологический, характер, физический, интеллектуальный, политический, сексуальный, взрослость, чувства, интуиция, половая жизнь.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence (i.e. 11-18 years) is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, when major changes occur in the physiological and psychological development of a person. During this period, bodies and mental states change, personality formation becomes more complex, social relations of young people, relations with family and society change. Adolescence is the period from 10-11 years to 14-15 years. Today's teenagers have some physical, mental and political advantages over their predecessors. Puberty, the process of socialization, and mental development manifest themselves earlier.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

For most schoolchildren, the transition to adolescence usually begins in the 5th grade. "A teenager is no longer a child, but not an adult either" - this definition indicates the important nature of adolescence. Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, characterized by physiological and psychological features. At this stage, children's physical and mental development accelerates, their interest in various things in life increases, their desire for something new intensifies, their character is formed, their spiritual world is enriched, and conflicts intensify.

Adolescence is a period of puberty, characterized by the emergence of new feelings, intuitions and complex issues related to sexuality. At this age, drastic changes in the development of a teenager begin to occur. These changes are physiological and psychological changes. Growth in height is uneven: girls grow by 5-7 cm, boys by 5-10 cm. Growth in height occurs due to the lengthening of the first femur and the expansion of the spine. As a result of changes in the oral cavity and larynx, the timbre of the voice also changes. This happens more often in boys than in girls. Boys' voices become muffled and booming. Although during this period the muscles grow and strengthen quickly, the rate of growth of the bones of the legs and arms lags behind. In teenagers, this feature makes them behave rudely, take long steps.

Physiological changes appear at the beginning of puberty and in this regard in the ideal development and growth of all organs of the body, the restructuring of the structures of cells and the body. Changes in the body are directly related to changes in the endocrine system of the teenager.

During this period, the function of the pituitary gland, one of the endocrine glands, is activated. Its activity enhances the growth of body tissues and the functioning of important endocrine glands (thyroid gland, adrenal glands and sex glands). As a result, growth in height accelerates, puberty occurs (development of the genitals, the appearance of secondary sex glands).

The chest also develops slowly compared to the height of the body. As a result, some teenagers' shoulders and chest become narrow, which in turn leads to a lack of oxygen and shortness of breath. Lack of oxygen impairs mental activity. During this period, blood vessels also thicken as the heart expands. The restructuring of the circulatory system, the stability of the autonomic nervous system disrupt blood circulation, and the teenager experiences a slight increase in blood pressure. During this period, the activity of the sex glands increases. As a result of the biological and physical changes that occur with the teenager, a radical change occurs in his mental world. Sexualization of behavioral features characteristic of adolescence. cannot be explained from the very beginning. Puberty affects the behavior of adolescents as a major biological factor, and this effect is more indirect than direct. Let's consider the features of physiological and psychological changes in adolescence:

1. Physiological Changes:

- **Physical Development:** During adolescence, the body undergoes rapid physical changes. This is due to specific hormonal changes (such as testosterone and estrogen). These hormones affect the development of the brain and body, thereby influencing appearance, muscle structure, and mobility.

- **Growth in Skeletal and Organ Size:** During this period, the adolescent's body length increases and the peak of body growth occurs. It affects motor skills, potassium-sodium metabolism, metabolic processes, and organizational functions.

- **Development of Reproductive Organs:** Males and females undergo significant changes in the reproductive system. In males, symptoms associated with ovulation (ovulation) appear, and in females, menstruation begins.

- **Puberty:** During adolescence, the readiness for beauty and physiological equality also contributes to psychological and social development through the process of vision.

2. Psychological Changes:

- **Formation of Personality:** During adolescence, specific personality traits, interests, and interests in important issues emerge. The person begins to accept his/her "I", needs and hopes in the new personality.

- **Social Relationships:** Teenagers become more independent in social relationships. They feel socially connected with adults, family members, as well as friends and community members.

- **Cognitive Development:** At this age, the brain learns to think complex thoughts and make positive decisions. Thus, teenagers acquire a unique ability to discuss and interpret life.

- **Emotional Changes:** As teenagers grow older, their emotional state often changes. This affects their internal needs and external influences, making new decisions, relationships with family and society.

- **Identity Formation:** Psychologically, teenagers try to identify their identity. It will be about passions, interests and defining identity.

CONCLUSION

Physiological and psychological changes are interconnected and are associated with the development of the mental state and the human body at this age, as well as physical changes.

During this period, it is important to maintain peace and balance, thereby helping to solve the individual problems of each teenager. Also, during adolescence, each person can experience a different number of physiological and psychological changes, so it is important to understand them correctly and provide support.

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